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ABSTRACT

The amount of soil organic carbon (SOC) in soils is a balance of the carbon input from plants and organic amendments and the carbon output due to mineralisation. Root carbon inputs have been shown to contribute 3-5 times more to soil organic carbon than aboveground plant carbon. We examined the biomass data from ten wheat varieties that were sampled at nine sites across Europe and derived allocations functions to investigate the potential of wheat variety selection on soil organic carbon on a European scale. Five versions of the widely applied SOC model RothC were applied that differed in the decomposition rates for straw and root carbon inputs: the standard RothC version, two versions calibrated for root and straw input, and two versions that were derived in Task 6.1 and take into account the observed three times higher SOC efficiency with two different dynamics in the RothC model (elevated root 1. resistance to decomposition and 2. carbon use efficiency). Each of the ten varieties' impact on SOC after 50 years was simulated applying their straw and root carbon input compared to the standard variety (defined as the ten-variety average) carbon input. Surprisingly, the maximum and minimum root varieties showed on average over all five RothC versions similar SOC changes and these changes were negative (-0.057 and -0.031 t SOC/ha). The maximum biomass variety performed best with a mean SOC gain of 0.383 t after 50 years and per hectare of European agricultural land (1.277 t SOC/ha in monoculture). The simulation results show that focussing on root biomass alone might result in increased root-derived SOC but might overall even lose soil organic carbon compared to the standard variety due to less above ground biomass carbon input to the soils.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

CUE	Carbon Use Efficiency
EU	European Union
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

Soil organic carbon is an effective measure to remove and store CO₂ and is one of the few available large-scale CO₂ sinks that could help mitigate climate change. The amount of soil organic carbon (SOC) in soils is a balance of the carbon input from plants and organic amendments and the carbon output due to mineralisation. It has been shown that the amount of soil organic carbon that evolves from carbon inputs depends on the part of the plant it comes from. Root biomass has observed to be about 2-5 times more “SOC efficient” than aboveground biomass (Balesdent&Balabane 1996, Rasse 2005, Kätterer 2001, Jackson2017, Villarino 2021). Reasons for this might be the e.g. physical protection due to micropores and/or enhanced C stabilization due to adsorption onto mineral surfaces (Villarino 2021). Unfortunately, only 16% of soil organic carbon models take this increased root SOC efficiency into account (MixRootC WP6.1). The widely applied SOC model RothC (Coleman&Jenkinson 1996) is one of the models that do not differentiate between C input origin, but calibrations from Dechow et al. using the DPM/RPM ratio, that splits up the carbon input into decomposable (D) and resistant (R) plant material, distinguish straw and root carbon (Dechow 2019). Two further versions of RothC were derived in WP6.1 by Frédéric Rees, that both implement three times higher SOC efficiency of root compared to straw carbon. The first version uses as well the DPM/RPM ratio and in this way assumes an increased chemical recalcitrance of root carbon. The second incorporates the finding of enhanced root carbon stabilization due to mineral adsorption, i.e. increased carbon use efficiency. Based on an extensive dataset of ten wheat varieties sampled at nine sites across Europe and the five model versions, we investigate the impact of wheat variety selection on soil organic carbon stocks. For this we choose three varieties:

- 1) the maximum root variety
- 2) the minimum root variety and
- 3) the maximum biomass variety, a variety that turned out to produce the maximum biomass and almost maximum yield, while root biomass comes second after the maximum root variety.

The maximum biomass variety is the “use case”, as farmers are interested in harvest maximum yields rather than roots and in this way will not accept yield losses for larger root carbon input. In the following, we will present the results of the SOC simulation for the three varieties combined with all five SOC models to investigate the potential of wheat variety selection on soil organic carbon.

2. Methods

The aim of WP6.3 is to estimate the change in SOC when the ten different wheat varieties are grown compared to the standard variety, which we defined as the average of the ten varieties. In order to simulate the SOC dynamics, the amount of carbon input from all then wheat varieties need to be estimated.

2.1. Allocation function wheat varieties

For this, an analysis of the European wheat variety dataset (WP3) was used, considering weather data, soil parameters and relationships of the plant parts to one another in order to derive a function for the wheat variety's root and straw carbon input.

A correlation analysis of biomasses with weather data showed little effect when annual weather data (mean annual precipitation, temperature, potential evapotranspiration) was applied. Dependencies of biomass amount on the weather conditions in certain months of the growing period showed larger correlations. However, we do not have the data of European growing periods and, thus, we are not able to apply this function. Hence, weather data cannot be used to derive the carbon input. Soil texture showed little prediction quality as the weather, especially on a European gradient, plays the dominant role.

Lastly, we investigated driver for wheat biomasses and found, in some cases, significant results. However, most of the derived linear functions of yield for straw and root biomass cross the average wheat variety linear function at some yield. Regression lines of two varieties cross, the C input difference between them changes significantly at this specific yield level. But due to small sampling number, the linear relations are only rough estimations of actual "population" behaviour. As a result, the Europe map would show SOC gains and losses for the same variety, depending on the yield level. A threshold that either does not exist or most likely is not the population threshold. In conclusion, although some linear functions for root and straw show statistical significance and explained yield variance well, they cannot be applied as their crossing leads to unreliable patterns of SOC change.

Following from the above analysis, we derived constant allocation coefficients for each variety, just as most of the common allocation functions do (Bolinder2007, Taghizadeh-Toosi2014, Jacobs2020, Keel2017). Hence, we assume proportionality of the plant's parts, e.g. root to shoot biomass.

2.2. European scale simulations for different varieties

2.2.1. SOC model applied

The SOC change that results from growing a variety instead of the standard variety is estimated with the soil organic carbon model RothC (Coleman&Jenkinson 1996) for topsoil (0-30 cm). We apply the standard version, two versions with modified DPM/RPM ratios that have been calibrated on 439 SOC data series from 36 arable long-term field experiments in Central and Northern Europe with two allocation functions (Dechow 2019, Franko 2012, Bolinder 2007). And two versions taking into account the three times higher SOC efficiency of root carbon input (WP6.1):

$$\text{Strategy 2: Root C is 3x more „resistant“} \rightarrow RPM_{ROOTS} = 3 \times RPM_{STRAW} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Strategy 3: Root C has a 3x higher CUE} \rightarrow BIO\&HUM_{ROOTS} = 3 \times BIO\&HUM_{STRAW} \quad (2)$$

RPM stand for the Resistant Plant Material pool, the fresh matter input pool with lower decomposition rates. And BIO&HUM are the pool for microbial biomass and humified organic matter. Carbon either enters the BIO and HUM pool or is mineralized to CO₂, i.e. carbon use efficiency (CUE).

2.2.2. Input data

The simulations are run across all countries of geographical Europe and on a 10 km grid. The following input data is applied:

1. Crop yield and harvested area (Grogan 2022): Based on GAEZ data from 2010, wheat yields and harvested areas are updated to 2015 considering national crop yield and area changes. Regional changes within countries are not taken into account but crop yield and area in each grid cell is adjusted with the same national factor.
2. Climate data (Parisse 2023): Temperature, precipitation and potential evapotranspiration data derived for RothC simulations in EJP SOIL CarboSeq project from the AgERA5 dataset.
3. Soil cover: NDVI-derived mean bare soil probability as in GSOCseq (FAO2020, Chapter 6.4).
4. Clay: OpenLandMap (Hengl 2018)

These data are converted and aggregated to the same grid and resolution used by CarboSeq, which is the European Lambert Azimuthal Equal-Area projection (EPSG:3035) and a 10 km grid. In this way, the resulting maps are easy to compare between the projects.

2.2.3. SOC Difference simulation

To simulate absolute soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks, carbon input data at European scale is needed from all C sources as organic amendments, cover crops and residue management. The challenge is that this data, at least at European scale, is not available or in coarse resolution, i.e. needs to be estimated. Thus, absolute SOC stocks and their trends would be a rather coarse or even incorrect that might rather confuse than help. We therefore will not simulate full SOC stocks but rather focus on the difference in SOC that is given by the change in carbon input compared to the standard wheat variety's input. This is possible because in RothC, as in many models, the decomposition rate in RothC follows first order kinetics, i.e. the decomposition rate is linearly related to SOC. This allows to do a simulation considering the difference in carbon input only:

$$C_{in_DIFF_roots} = C_{in_Variety_roots} - C_{in_StandardVariety_roots} \quad (3)$$

$$C_{in_DIFF_hr} = C_{in_Variety_hr} - C_{in_StandardVariety_hr} \quad (4)$$

This results in the SOC difference. Hence, our results show how much SOC we lose or gain when one variety is grown instead of the standard variety. Wheat cultivation areas are largest in France (5.2 million ha), Germany (3.1), Poland (2.4), Romania (2.1), Spain (2.1), Italy (1.8) and UK (1.7).

3. Results: European scale simulations for selected varieties

The SOC difference is given in t SOC per average agricultural area hectare in the grid cell and SOC losses are marked in red, SOG gains are marked in green. The scale is the same for all maps. The following SOC simulation results have been obtained.

Figure 1: SOC difference per hectare agricultural land after 50 years for the **maximum root variety** Bernstein simulated with the five versions of RothC.

Figure 1: SOC difference per hectare agricultural land after 50 years for the **minimum root variety** Julie simulated with the five versions of RothC.

Figure 3: SOC difference per hectare agricultural land after 50 years for the **maximum biomass variety** Aurelius simulated with the five versions of RothC.

The three figures above show the outcome of the simulations after 50 years, run with each of the five RothC versions and for each of the three varieties maximum root (Bernstein), minimum root (Julie) and maximum biomass (Aurelius). In the order of the applied RothC versions from top-left to bottom-right, the root decomposition rate decreases and straw decomposition rate increases, leading to ever larger/smaller contributions of roots and straw, respectively.

The maximum biomass variety outperforms the maximum root variety by far, as its combined above-average straw and root carbon input change (Table 2: 0.157 t/ha/y) exceeds the maximum root variety's C input change (-0.058) by far. Maximum and minimum root varieties, on average across all RothC simulations, show a slight decline of European SOC stocks. The minimum root variety reduces SOC even less than the maximum root variety, as Bernstein shows the lowest C input difference of straw and root combined (-0.058 t/ha).

Variety	mean European SOC difference [t/ha/y]		Total
	roots	straw	
Aurelius share	0.144	0.239	0.383
... monoculture	0.482	0.795	1.277
Bernstein share	0.227	-0.284	-0.057
... monoculture	0.759	-0.948	-0.189
Julie share	-0.321	0.290	-0.031
... monoculture	-1.071	0.966	-0.105

Table 1: The mean SOC difference after 50 years per hectare of European agricultural land that results from growing each of the three chosen varieties instead of the standard variety (defined as average over all ten wheat varieties). As in the maps above, the losses take into account that wheat is cultivated only on a share of total agricultural land (share) as well as the SOC loss from growing wheat in monoculture.

Variety	mean C input difference [t/ha/y]		Total
	roots	straw	
Aurelius	0.046	0.110	0.156
Bernstein	0.073	-0.131	-0.058
Julie	-0.103	0.134	0.031

Table 2: The mean carbon input difference per year and hectare of wheat cultivation that results from growing each of the three chosen varieties instead of the standard variety (defined as average over all ten wheat varieties).

4. Discussion

Surprisingly, the maximum root biomass variety Bernstein on average over all RothC versions loses SOC, contrary to the expectations (-0.057 t SOC/ha). Just as the minimum root variety Julie (-0.031), that was expected to result in strong SOC decline. It is interesting to see how contributions from straw-derived SOC to overall SOC determine the resulting SOC difference. The maximum biomass variety, that is as well the variety with second most root and yield biomasses, gains most root and straw biomass-derived carbon and thus also shows total SOC gain. Therefore, it shows a comparably extreme increase of SOC. Although, when considering the SOC result of all ten varieties (will be part of a future publication), no strong straw-root trade-off can be observed ($R^2=0.22$). The result clearly shows that a) straw matters for SOC and b) choosing the maximum root variety does not guarantee SOC increase.

Future biomass demand will likely drive biomass price and might favor straw-rich varieties over root-rich varieties, possibly putting pressure on SOC due to lower root C input in addition to the SOC loss due to higher straw removal.

The results, especially the absolute numbers, need to be taken with caution as there are large sources of uncertainties: First, we used an outstanding but still small European dataset (WP3) with too few replicates (only one year sampling) and sites to derive allocation functions from it to apply it to Europe, with its vast climatic and pedoclimatic gradients. Second, stubble and chaff were not sampled and, therefore, not considered in the simulations as any estimation of their biomass in dependence on straw biomass did not seem to be straight forward. However, at least a slight positive relationship between stubble/chaff and straw could be expected and would then lead to even more contributions from aboveground residues. Third, we did not consider rhizodeposition to change with root biomass changes as it is not clear whether the rhizodeposition/root ratio would stay constant or whether there is a trade-off (more roots => more nutrients can be reached => less rhizodeposition (?)). Uncertainty arises as well from the structure chosen for the allocation functions. The constant allocation coefficients assume that straw and root biomass relate proportionally to yield, i.e. 10% more yield leads to 10% more straw and roots. Opposed to the observed linearity, this will lead to underestimation of carbon input for low yields and overestimation for high yields.

As an outlook, the European dataset allows for a “high-precision” allocation function based on monthly climate data, when growing period data for its application is available. Integrating weather variables into the allocation functions, particularly precipitation, resulted in a substantial increase in explained variance, as indicated by high R^2 values. The SOC simulations showed a huge range for the five versions with their different considerations of decomposition rates for root- and straw-derived carbon inputs. Research efforts should be made to a) investigate more the different effects of C input type on SOC and b) this should be better/at all integrated in SOC models, especially when straw removal is simulated as the effect of SOC will be overestimated with most common SOC models that do not distinguish their SOC efficiency.

5. Conclusion

Variety selection might have great potential for future considerations of enhanced SOC and/or biomass production. From our results, based on a small dataset, it shows that straw matters and, therefore, maximum overall biomass production of cultivars should be chosen over maximum root biomass in order to enhance SOC. Considering root or straw biomass only neglects possible trade-offs, that may be enhanced in the simulation due to different decomposition rates. Future biomass price rise poses a potential threat to SOC stocks due to straw-rich variety selection over root-rich varieties (as far as this trade-off exists) that might lead to larger SOC declines due to decreased root C input in addition to the impact of straw removal. The results presented above will be published together with further results of all varieties and further research on the dataset.

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